

THE WORD STRESS OF UZBEK, KARAKALPAK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation:

Word stress is present only in certain languages, known as lexical stress. Linguists have different perspectives on accents, but their research helps us gain a better understanding of this phenomenon. As for lexical stress is a significant supersegmental unit with distinct articulatory and acoustic properties. Factors such as pitch, intensity, duration, and frequency play a role in the formation of lexical stress, with one or two factors sometimes prevailing. The thesis is aimed at providing sufficient information about word stress in Karakalpak, English as well as Uzbek languages.

Key words: stress, pitch, acoustic signs of a dynamic accent, the tension, the muscles of the speech organs, an accent, percussion, suprasegmental feature.

As it is scientifically proven that phonetic phenomena, such as accents, serve specific functions in languages and are not arbitrary.

In three languages (Karakalpak, English and Uzbek) monosyllabic, two-syllable, or polysyllabic words with adjectival meanings have a single accent, known as the head accent. Vowels play a more crucial role than consonants in determining stress. Accent classification is based on identifying the dominant factor involved in stress formation. Since both English and Uzbek prioritize certain factors over others, these languages can be categorized as dynamic accented languages.

In English, the gradation property of lexical stress is more significant compared to Uzbek, Karakalpak languages. Linguists hold diverse opinions on accent classification, and no single perspective can be considered superior. In Uzbek, there is insufficient evidence and basis for accent gradation, meaning that there is no need for different levels of lexical stress. Consequently, this aspect is not fully explained in available sources.

English is considered a freely accented language, as accent patterns in this language often deviate from general rules, making it unpredictable. On the other hand, in Uzbek, the accent is predominantly placed on the final syllable of a word. However, due to certain linguistic phenomena, such as inflections and

adverbs, the accent can occasionally be placed on syllables preceding the final one.

However, in Karakalpak, English and Uzbek, the accent placement can be influenced by linguistic phenomena such as inflections, suffixes, and derived words. Determining the location of lexical stress in English is a complex process that has sparked debates among scholars. There are three main trends - recessive, retentive, and rhythmic - that help determine stress placement, but due to numerous exceptions, they are not always reliable. Therefore, it is convenient to consider factors such as word morphology, syllable count, phonological structure, and word families to determine stress, although exceptional cases must also be taken into account. Derived words and adverbs have a significant impact on the lexical accent of those languages.

In English, determining the accent in compound words and phrases relies on analyzing their constituent elements, conducting semantic and orthographic analysis, and considering differences between British and American pronunciation. In both Uzbek and English, auxiliary words tend to be unstressed. Unlike English, abbreviations are also usually unstressed in Uzbek. The accentual syllable structures of English words are based on stress levels and how stress is distributed across syllables within a word. These patterns are influenced by the morphological type of word formation, the number of syllables, affixes and suffixes, as well as the semantic significance of the base.

In conclusion, word stress serves three crucial functions in languages: generation, limitation, and differentiation. No other linguistic phenomenon can fulfill these tasks in the context of accent. Lexical stress is essential for expressing stylistic meaning in speech and contributes to the overall meaning of words in Karakalpak, English as well as Uzbek languages.

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